

NMR studies of model biological membranes and whole cells[†]

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Abstract : Cells are the basic units of living systems. The interior of cells is separated from the extra-cellular medium by semi-permeable barriers (membranes), which separate the inside from the outside of the cells. Membranes allow passage from inside to outside of the cells and *vice-versa* in a highly selective manner. In this paper, we have illustrated how drugs change the permeability of cell membranes, and how this information can be used for designing novel drug molecules. Studies on NMR of intact cells have been illustrated with a particular cellular system, spermatozoa. It has been shown how NMR can provide information on the bioenergetics of intact and alive cells. Studies on body tissues can be conducted using solid-state NMR techniques. Such studies allow learning of the chemical processes that take place in living systems, ranging from biological molecules to living systems.

Introduction

Considering that most of the chemists reading this journal are not familiar with biochemistry and biophysics, we will explain some basic principles involved in the chemistry of living systems, before giving details of the subject touched in this paper.

Molecules of living systems can be divided into three categories. (i) Small molecules, such as metal ions, water and amino acids. An important molecule in this category is adenosine tri phosphate (ATP), which provides energy to living systems. The Na⁺/K⁺ balance is also important for human health. (ii) Medium size molecules, which include lipids and sugars. Glucose and fructose are the primary molecules in the energy cycle of living systems. (iii) Large molecules such as proteins, nucleic acids and carbohydrates. Both proteins and nucleic acids have well defined three dimensional (3D) structures, which confer specificity on their function. One of the important functions of proteins is to catalyse biochemical reactions in the body. DNA and RNA are involved in the genetic control. One also finds conjugates of these molecules, such as glycoprotein and glycolipids.

Four nuclei are normally used for studying chemistry of living systems. These are : ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N and ³¹P. Organic chemists are familiar with the use of the first two

nuclei for solving chemical structures. In biological systems, there are a large number of molecules, and the molecular weights of several molecules are large. This leads to the problems of resolution and assignments in NMR spectroscopy. Further, since *in vivo* concentrations, of most of the molecules is small, there is the problem of sensitivity. All studies are conducted in presence of water, and the peak due to water has to be suppressed. These problems have been solved through the use of Fourier Transform (FT) NMR spectroscopy. One of the important contributions of NMR has been to establish three dimensional (3D) structures of large biological molecules such as proteins and nucleic acids. Such molecules have thousands of ¹H and there are problems of resolution, sensitivity and resolution. Multi-dimensional FT NMR studies have been used for this purpose¹. On the other extreme are studies on whole body and organ, which includes Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (MRS). These topics are not the subjects of this article. Here, we shall concentrate on cells and tissues. Fig. 1 gives a chart of the flow of information from molecules to living systems in biological systems. ³¹P is an important nucleus because it provides information on bioenergetics, and in particular levels of energy rich compounds such as ATP and phosphocreatine (PCr) (Fig. 2).

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Flow of information and controls in biological systems. The function is controlled at several levels. It is important to understand chemistry and biology of living systems at all levels shown in the above diagram.

Fig. 1. A schematic view of flow of information in biological systems from molecules to living systems.

Fig. 2. ^{31}P NMR spectrum from a typical cell.

Cellular NMR spectroscopy : The boundaries of living cells act as semi-permeable membranes. Biological membranes allow passage of molecules from inside to outside and *vice-versa* in a highly selective manner. Membranes are essentially built of lipids and proteins. They also contain some sugars in the form of glycol-lipids and glycol-proteins. Lipids have a molecular weight in the range 500 to 800 Da. The molecular weights of proteins are several thousand Daltons. Thus, there are several thousand lipid molecules for each protein molecule. Therefore, membranes can be viewed as a matrix of lipids with the proteins embedded in this matrix. Lipids are essential components of cell walls. In addition, they act as cofactors for enzymes, electron carriers and as energy source for cells. A unique feature of lipids is that unlike proteins and nucleic acids, they are insoluble in water, but are soluble in chloroform. A large fraction of cellular lipids are phospholipids. They are built from two fatty acid chains, attached at C1 and C2 position of a glycerol moiety. These chains may contain 14 to 24 carbons. The third position is attached a phosphorylated alcohol such as choline. In the experiments discussed here, 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC) has been

used. Blood cells also contain a neutral lipid, cholesterol, which is a neutral lipid and is hydrophobic. It is responsible for some of the diseases in humans.

A characteristic feature of phospholipids is that they have well defined hydrophilic and hydrophobic regions. When dispersed in water, the hydrophilic regions try to make contact with water, while the hydrophobic regions try to keep away. This leads to a bilayer aggregate structure. In a cell, there is a closed overall structure. Because of the relatively free motion around C-C single bonds, lipids have a fluid structure. Proteins are embedded in this structure. In a cell, the proteins on the two sides are different. This asymmetry controls the biological functions on the two sides.

Lipid bilayers and drug-membrane interaction

We shall divide the discussion in two parts. First we shall discuss studies on model membranes, which are simpler to study. We will then focus on studies of whole cells and tissues.

Model membranes : Since the NMR studies on intact cells is difficult, studies are often done on model membranes^{2,3}. In fact, a wealth of information has been gathered on drug-membrane interaction using model-membranes. For preparing lipid-bilayers, one disperses the lipids in water, and then sonicates this suspension. This leads to spherical vesicles, which can be used for model studies. Drug or protein can be incorporated into these vesicles. An important property of model bilayers is that as the temperature is lowered, they show a liquid crystalline to gel phase transition. There is a very narrow range of temperature in which the lipid bilayers are liquid crystalline. The cells choose the lipids such that the cell membranes are liquid crystalline at the ambient temperature. At lower temperatures, the lipid vesicles go into a gel

phase. At higher temperatures the vesicles break.

Drug-membrane interaction : NMR has been extensively used to study localization of drugs in model membranes as well conformation and intermolecular interaction. A number of compounds act by changing the fluidity of biological membranes. For example, the accumulation of cholesterol in veins, make them rigid and hurts the flow of blood, leading to blood pressure and associated diseases. The drug molecules can reverse this rigidity. A number of studies have been conducted to study interaction of membrane active drugs with model membranes. Such studies help in drug-design.

NMR studies on intact cells

Cells are the units of living system. A cell conducts hundreds of biological reactions with the help of enzymes as catalysts. These include bioenergetics, biosynthesis, and molecular transport. Some of these functions may be impaired due to disease. NMR has the capability of studying these processes in healthy and diseased individuals at the level of cells, tissues and organs. In a living system a very large number of reactions take place. Cell metabolism consists of a highly intricate net-work of coupled biochemical reactions. Each metabolic pathway consists of a series of individual reactions, which are coupled to each other. The energy to the cells is provided by a series of oxidative reactions which break molecules such as glucose, amino acids and fatty acids, and store the energy thus released in the form of ATP. When energy is required by the cell, ATP is hydrolysed to ADP and inorganic phosphate and the energy released in this reaction can be used by the cell. Another energy rich compound is phosphocreatine (PCr).

There are three major steps in energy producing metabolism : (i) glycolysis, (ii) citric acid and (iii) oxidative phosphorylation. Each of these processes involves several oxidative reactions, and lead to production of ATP. All three NMR active nuclei, ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P have been used for studying metabolism in cells, tissues and organs.

NMR studies on spermatozoa : The first challenge in *in-cell* NMR studies or on work on tissues and body fluids is to obtain samples with good homogeneity. The cells should be kept alive and metabolically active during NMR measurements. Thus, low concentration of the cells has to be used. However, this comes at the expense of reduced sensitivity. The cell suspension is made as homogeneous as possible. A regulated medium has to be used. The second challenge is due to the fact that each

cell has a large number of metabolites at relatively low concentrations. This leads to the problems of sensitivity, resolution and assignments in the spectra. Use of multi-dimensional FT NMR spectroscopy has been used to overcome these problems. *In-cell* NMR studies have been done both on mammalian systems and on plant cells.

Several aspects of information can be obtained from cellular NMR. We will illustrate this from NMR from studies on mammalian spermatozoa, which have been studied for a number of years in TIFR⁴. The reasons for choosing these cells are : (i) Spermatozoa are paternal cells in mammalian systems, (ii) Cells are readily available from slaughter houses or from volunteers, (iii) The metabolic behaviour has wide implications in the understanding of reproductive biology, artificial insemination, fertility control and animal husbandry, (iv) Under anaerobic conditions spermatozoa survive only on glycolysis and (v) The cells do not form lumps or settle in a NMR tube.

The overall structure of these cells can be divided into three parts : (i) a head, which contains the paternal chromatin, (ii) mid-piece, which contains enzymes, which are released during fertilization of the egg and (iii) a tail which allows movement (called motility) of spermatozoa. Motility and fertilizing activity are the major markers of sperm activity. During the maturation of the cells in parental reproductive organ, the maturation takes place in three stages : *caput* is the birth place and cells are least matured. In *cauda* region the cells are fully matured.

Fig. 3. Steps in glycolysis, which is bioenergetics path used by spermatozoa.

Sperm survive on glycolysis. Glycolysis takes place in 8 steps (Fig. 3). The overall reaction during can be repre-

Fig. 4. 2D ^{13}C - ^1H spectra from least matured (*caput* region) and fully matured (*cauda* region). Changes in the levels of metabolites during cell maturation can be picked up. In particular, note that hypo-taurine is switched on once the cells are in a matured state.

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^1H and natural abundance ^{13}C NMR allows detection of molecules in the cells through ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^{13}C 2D NMR techniques (Fig. 4). Each step in the glycolytic pathway (Fig. 4) can be monitored through ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy. The wealth of information that is present in these spectra is obvious from this figure. Each of the metabolite can be detected from ^1H - ^{13}C 2D NMR. ATP and ADP levels can be monitored using ^{31}P NMR. In the *caput* region one sees only ADP signals. ATP level increases as the cells mature. The total inositol decreases with maturation, while the level the concentration of several amino acids increases. An unusual amino acid found in matured spermatozoa is hypotaurine. This amino acid is important for capacitation and fertilization is weak in *caput* region. The effect of external factors, on glycolysis can be determined using NMR. Effect of exogenous compounds such as anti-fertility drugs on glycolysis can be monitored.

NMR studies on tissues : Tissues differ from biological cells in that they are solid like materials. Therefore, solid-state NMR techniques have to be used. Cells in freshly excised tissues are active. Normally, tissues are excised from host, kept frozen and thawed just before taking the spectrum. With proper care, one can get the

metabolic state of the tissue at the time of excision. Using Magic angle spinning (MAS) high resolution spectra of tissues can be obtained. Line widths of the order of 20 Hz can be achieved in favourable cases. Such studies help in optimising drug delivery. MAS has been used to study tissues from brain, kidney, roots and leaves. Such studies have found applications in gene cloning, drug development and health care.

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